

Technical Appendix

TED-DTMoA: Tri-Comparison Expertise Decision for Drug-Target Mechanism of Action

Lingxiang Jia^{a,c}, Zipeng Zhong^a, Shaolun Yao^a, Jie Song^{a,b,c}, Mingli Song^{a,c} and Zunlei Feng^{a,b,c,*}

^aState Key Laboratory of Blockchain and Data Security, Zhejiang University

^bSchool of Software Technology, Zhejiang University

^cHangzhou High-Tech Zone (Binjiang) Institute of Blockchain and Data Security

A Detail of TED-DTMoA method

Detailed information about the proposed TED-DTMoA method is provided as follows. First, as shown in Appendix Table 1, the key notations and the corresponding definitions are summarized for clarification. Then, the first step of TED-DTMoA about task decomposition is elaborated. Next, the algorithm of class-balanced decision voting module is provided as the supplement of the introduction of the main paper. Finally, the theoretical analysis of TED-DTMoA is discussed in detail.

A.1 Task Decomposition

The original drug-target mechanism of action (DTMoA) prediction task is denoted as a multi-classification task with N classes. Each sub-task aims for the classification of only two classes, resulting in a total of $C_N^2 = \frac{N*(N-1)}{2}$ sub-tasks. Each sub-task is trained by a dedicated expertise model to extract knowledge related to the corresponding two classes. To effectively determine the classification boundaries of mechanism classes, we introduce an additional class \mathcal{N}_\otimes for samples that do not belong to the selected two classes.

Taking the classification of the two DTMoA classes \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} as an example, we first extract the class-related samples from the original dataset \mathcal{D} , and denote them as $\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{A}$, $\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{B}$. Meanwhile, the samples $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}$ belonging to class \mathcal{N}_\otimes are randomly sampled from the dataset excluding class \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , with the total number of samples equal to the mean number of samples in class \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , i.e., $\frac{|\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{A}|+|\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{B}|}{2}$. This sampling strategy is adopted to achieve a balanced three-class prediction task and mitigate the severe long-tailed problem that may exist in the original dataset. Ultimately, the training dataset for this task $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}}$ is the combination of three datasets $\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{A}$, $\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{B}$, $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}$. The relationship of the three datasets and the ground truth label $y_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}}$ are represented as follows:

$$\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes} \subseteq \mathcal{D} - (\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{D}_\mathcal{B}), \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}} = \{\mathcal{D}_\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{D}_\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}\}, \quad (1)$$

$$y_{\mathcal{A}/\mathcal{B}} \in \{\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{N}_\otimes\}. \quad (2)$$

A.2 Algorithm of Class-balanced Decision Voting

Here, the detailed algorithm of the class-balanced decision voting module is shown as Appendix Algorithm 1.

* Corresponding Author. Email: zunleifeng@zju.edu.cn

Algorithm 1 Class-balanced decision voting process for the final prediction.

Input: The initial prediction results of all the expertise models \mathbf{Q} ; N is the number of the DTMoA classes; β_R is the base reward score; β_P is the base penalty score; \mathbf{H} is the balanced penalty weight vector.

Output: Prediction \hat{y} .

```

1:  $\mathbf{Y} \leftarrow (0, \dots, 0)_N$ ; //Initialized vote results
2: for  $q_{i,j}$  in  $\mathbf{Q}$  do
3:   if  $q_{i,j}$  is 0 then
4:      $\mathbf{Y}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}_i + \beta_R$ ;
5:   else if  $q_{i,j}$  is 1 then
6:      $\mathbf{Y}_j \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}_j + \beta_R$ ;
7:   else if  $q_{i,j}$  is -1 then
8:      $\mathbf{Y}_i \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}_i - \beta_P \cdot \mathbf{H}_i$ ;
9:      $\mathbf{Y}_j \leftarrow \mathbf{Y}_j - \beta_P \cdot \mathbf{H}_j$ ;
10:  end if
11: end for
12: return  $\hat{y} \leftarrow \text{argmax}(\mathbf{Y})$ 

```

A.3 Theoretical Analysis

The tri-comparison strategy provides a comprehensive solution for multi-class classification, particularly in long-tailed tasks like DTMoA prediction. By integrating decision boundary theory and error decomposition, it enhances both performance and generalization.

In traditional binary classification, decision boundaries (e.g., $f_{i,j}(x)$ for classes i and j) often suffer from noise and bias due to overlapping regions from unrelated samples, especially in long-tailed distributions. The tri-comparison strategy addresses this by introducing class \mathcal{N}_\otimes , with a new decision boundary $f_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}(x)$, creating three distinct regions: $\mathbb{R}^d = \{x : f_i(x) > f_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}(x)\} \cup \{x : f_j(x) > f_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}(x)\} \cup \{x : f_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}(x) > \max(f_i(x), f_j(x))\}$. This refinement in decision boundaries reduces the noise caused by ambiguous samples, ensuring clearer separation between classes and laying a foundation for improved classification accuracy.

Furthermore, in binary classification, the overall error ϵ_{binary} is dominated by the false negative rate of minority classes and the false positive rate of majority classes. By explicitly isolating unrelated samples into class \mathcal{N}_\otimes , the classification error is redefined as $\epsilon_{\text{tri}} = \epsilon_{\text{false positive}} + \epsilon_{\text{false negative}} + \epsilon_{\mathcal{N}_\otimes}$. This separation reduces the overlap between positive and negative classes, significantly lower-

Table 1: Notations and Definitions.

Notation	Definition
N	The number of DTMoA classes.
\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}	The abbreviation for the simplification of the mechanism class pair for the sub-task.
\mathcal{N}_{\otimes}	The introduced third option for each sub-task, alongside the two selected classes.
\mathcal{G}	$\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ indicates a molecular graph, and \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E} indicate the set of atoms and the set of chemical bonds, respectively.
\mathcal{V}	The set of atoms of \mathcal{G} .
\mathcal{E}	The set of chemical bonds of \mathcal{G} .
$f_{\mathcal{M}}$	The input feature dimensional of atoms in the drug \mathcal{M} .
$f_{\mathcal{T}}$	The input feature dimensional of the protein \mathcal{T} .
$d_{\mathcal{M}}$	The output feature dimensional of the molecular graph \mathcal{G} of drug \mathcal{M} .
$d_{\mathcal{T}}$	The output feature dimensional of the protein \mathcal{T} .
$\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{M}}^{(0)}$	The initial atom feature for molecule \mathcal{M} . $\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{M}}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{ \mathcal{V} \times f_{\mathcal{M}}}$.
$\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{M}}^{(l)}$	The input atom feature for molecule \mathcal{M} of GCN layer l .
$\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{M}}$	The output graph feature for molecule \mathcal{M} . $\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{M}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathcal{M}}}$.
$\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{T}}^{(0)}$	The initial feature for target protein \mathcal{T} . $\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{T}}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{f_{\mathcal{T}}}$.
$\mathbf{X}_{\mathcal{T}}^{(l)}$	The input feature for target protein \mathcal{T} of 1D CNN layer l .
$\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{T}}$	The output feature for target protein \mathcal{T} . $\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{T}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathcal{T}}}$.
$\mathbf{Z}^{(0)}$	The joint representation generated by the combination of $\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{M}}$ and $\mathbf{Z}_{\mathcal{T}}$ and meanwhile the input feature of the predictor module. $\mathbf{Z}^{(0)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\mathcal{M}}+d_{\mathcal{T}}}$.
$\mathbf{Z}^{(l)}$	The input feature of MLP layer l .
\mathbf{Q}	The initial prediction results obtained from the expertise models. $\mathbf{Q} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}^{\frac{N \times (N-1)}{2}}$.
$q_{i,j}$	The prediction result for the sub-task of classifying class i and class j . $q_{i,j} \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$.
\mathbf{Y}	The final voting results of N classes. $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^N$.
\mathbf{H}	The class-balanced weight vector for penalty score of different classes. $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^N$.
β_R	The base reward score for expertise predictions.
β_P	The base penalty score for expertise predictions.

ing $\epsilon_{\text{false positive}}$ and $\epsilon_{\text{false negative}}$, and consequently decreasing the total error. The tri-comparison strategy thus moves beyond simple noise reduction, actively addressing imbalances in class representation to improve classification reliability.

B Detail of Experiment

For further analysis, the details about datasets, implementations, and experimental results are provided. First, the dataset preprocessing steps and the statistical details of the preprocessed three datasets are outlined. Then, comprehensive performance comparisons of DeepPurpose and BioT5+ method are presented. Next, the implementation details of the proposed method and the computation resources of all the experiments are elaborated. Finally, we introduce these experimental metrics in detail for a better understanding.

B.1 Dataset Preprocessing

For experiments of DTMoA prediction, the following steps are applied to the two datasets GtoPdb-MoA and ChEBML-MoA before put into training or test:

Domain Filtering. Only retain drug-target pairs that are relevant to humans and have complete field information, that is, drug SMILES and target protein identifier SwissProt;

Validity Check. Use RDKit package [8] to determine whether the drug SMILES is illegal;

Data Match. Match the corresponding protein sequence in the UniProt database [1] according to the SwissProt identifier;

Statistical Analysis. Analyze the DTMoA classes field (prediction label) of the currently screened dataset, including agonist and inhibitor, and divide into the head and tail classes.

After preprocessing, we obtain the specific datasets for long-tailed DTMoA prediction. 13,389 and 829 triplets, of which triplet format

Table 2: Detailed information of three DTMoA datasets.

Dataset	#Class	#Samples	#Total
GtoPdb-MoA	Inhibitor	5,672	13,381
	Agonist	3,234	
	Antagonist	2,829	
	Allosteric modulator	581	
	Channel blocker	499	
	Activator	358	
	None	165	
ChEBML-MoA	Gating inhibitor	43	829
	Inhibitor	421	
	Antagonist	213	
	Agonist	181	
	Channel blocker	12	
GtoPdb-GPCRs	Allosteric modulator	2	5,319
	Agonist	2606	
	Antagonist	2399	
	Non-target	314	

is (drug SMILES, target sequence, DTMoA class), are obtained for the processed GtoPdb-MoA and ChEBML-MoA. The former two are used as the model input and the latter as the ground truth label.

B.2 Dataset Details

In this paper, three DTMoA datasets are used to evaluate the efficacy of the proposed method. Each dataset encompasses different DTMoA classes and their corresponding sample number. Appendix Table 2 provides a detailed presentation of each dataset, including the types of DTMoAs, the sample number with different mechanisms, and the total number of the whole dataset. All these datasets exhibit the long-tailed distribution. All these samples are structured into triplet scheme (drug SMILES, target sequence, DTMoA class).

Furthermore, the relationships among the three datasets are clarified as follows: (1) GtoPdb-MoA serves as the training set for 5-fold cross-validation and internal testing. (2) ChEBML-MoA acts as

Table 3: Prediction performance of DeepPurpose for DTMoA prediction on the GtoPdb-MoA dataset. The table displays the prediction results of all the 49 combinations (7 drug encoders and 7 target encoders), which is an extension of Table 1. All the results are presented as “mean \pm standard deviation” and the best one shown in Table 1 is the combination of “Daylight + AAC”.

Methods		Metrics	
Drug Encoder	Target Encoder	Accuracy \uparrow	F1 score \uparrow
Morgan	AAC	0.901 \pm 0.005	0.775 \pm 0.021
	Conjoint_triad	0.898 \pm 0.001	0.787 \pm 0.026
	PseudoAAC	0.814 \pm 0.005	0.656 \pm 0.041
	Quasi-seq	0.800 \pm 0.004	0.632 \pm 0.024
	CNN	0.882 \pm 0.005	0.738 \pm 0.041
	CNN_RNN	0.881 \pm 0.003	0.735 \pm 0.012
	Transformer	0.869 \pm 0.006	0.721 \pm 0.025
Pubchem	AAC	0.904 \pm 0.003	0.785 \pm 0.019
	Conjoint_triad	0.906 \pm 0.007	0.790 \pm 0.029
	PseudoAAC	0.837 \pm 0.007	0.707 \pm 0.029
	Quasi-seq	0.809 \pm 0.005	0.643 \pm 0.028
	CNN	0.898 \pm 0.004	0.764 \pm 0.022
	CNN_RNN	0.895 \pm 0.006	0.770 \pm 0.017
	Transformer	0.880 \pm 0.005	0.746 \pm 0.022
Daylight	AAC	0.907 \pm 0.008	0.804 \pm 0.031
	Conjoint_triad	0.903 \pm 0.009	0.788 \pm 0.031
	PseudoAAC	0.827 \pm 0.009	0.702 \pm 0.032
	Quasi-seq	0.801 \pm 0.003	0.659 \pm 0.025
	CNN	0.899 \pm 0.005	0.776 \pm 0.023
	CNN_RNN	0.896 \pm 0.004	0.778 \pm 0.021
	Transformer	0.879 \pm 0.004	0.757 \pm 0.017
rdkit	AAC	0.902 \pm 0.006	0.789 \pm 0.029
	Conjoint_triad	0.904 \pm 0.007	0.796 \pm 0.021
	PseudoAAC	0.831 \pm 0.006	0.690 \pm 0.015
	Quasi-seq	0.797 \pm 0.010	0.654 \pm 0.041
	CNN	0.896 \pm 0.010	0.762 \pm 0.048
	CNN_RNN	0.898 \pm 0.003	0.789 \pm 0.021
	Transformer	0.884 \pm 0.006	0.759 \pm 0.012
CNN	AAC	0.893 \pm 0.010	0.748 \pm 0.035
	Conjoint_triad	0.895 \pm 0.006	0.770 \pm 0.024
	PseudoAAC	0.820 \pm 0.006	0.641 \pm 0.016
	Quasi-seq	0.789 \pm 0.010	0.584 \pm 0.019
	CNN	0.899 \pm 0.003	0.768 \pm 0.037
	CNN_RNN	0.869 \pm 0.015	0.719 \pm 0.030
	Transformer	0.884 \pm 0.004	0.751 \pm 0.009
CNN_RNN	AAC	0.893 \pm 0.008	0.762 \pm 0.029
	Conjoint_triad	0.890 \pm 0.011	0.768 \pm 0.045
	PseudoAAC	0.813 \pm 0.010	0.668 \pm 0.042
	Quasi-seq	0.795 \pm 0.006	0.627 \pm 0.030
	CNN	0.886 \pm 0.006	0.771 \pm 0.015
	CNN_RNN	0.878 \pm 0.003	0.749 \pm 0.015
	Transformer	0.874 \pm 0.002	0.743 \pm 0.012
Transformer	AAC	0.901 \pm 0.008	0.789 \pm 0.013
	Conjoint_triad	0.901 \pm 0.013	0.795 \pm 0.029
	PseudoAAC	0.817 \pm 0.004	0.681 \pm 0.028
	Quasi-seq	0.818 \pm 0.010	0.668 \pm 0.047
	CNN	0.891 \pm 0.002	0.759 \pm 0.026
	CNN_RNN	0.907 \pm 0.005	0.792 \pm 0.011
	Transformer	0.884 \pm 0.007	0.751 \pm 0.032

an entirely independent external test set, evaluated using the models trained on GtoPdb-MoA, ensuring no overlap with GtoPdb-MoA and thus guaranteeing fairness in testing. (3) GtoPdb-GPCRs, a subset of GtoPdb-MoA related to the GPCRs target family, is used to validate the generalization ability of the proposed method.

Table 4: Performance and parameter comparison with cross-modal LLM BioT5+. Note that the number of trained parameters for TED-DTMoA is presented as the total sum of all 28 sub-task models.

Methods	#Param.	GtoPdb-MoA		ChEBML-MoA	
		Accuracy \uparrow	F1 score \uparrow	Accuracy \uparrow	F1 score \uparrow
BioT5+	252M	0.920 \pm 0.003	0.829 \pm 0.022	0.954 \pm 0.002	0.767 \pm 0.018
TED-DTMoA	10M	0.924\pm0.004	0.834\pm0.012	0.961\pm0.003	0.789\pm0.040

B.3 Performance Comparison with DeepPurpose

DeepPurpose [4] supports training of customized DTI prediction models by implementing different compound and protein encoders and over 50 neural architectures. Here we adopt the pair combination of 7 drug encoders and 7 target encoders to display the performance. Appendix Table 3 presents the prediction performance of all the 49 combinations on the GtoPdb-MoA dataset, which is an extension of Table 1 in the main paper. All the results are presented as “mean \pm standard deviation” and the best one shown in Table 1 is the combination of “Daylight + AAC” architecture.

B.4 Performance Comparison with BioT5+

BioT5+ [16] is a cross-modal pre-trained LLM with 252M parameters, designed to enhance cross-modal integration in biology. Appendix Table 4 shows that TED-DTMoA, with only 1/25 of the parameters, still outperforms BioT5+. This demonstrates that even with a significantly smaller model size, our method achieves superior performance, highlighting its balance between parameter efficiency and task accuracy.

B.5 Implementation Details

To accurately evaluate model performance and prevent overfitting, we use 5-fold cross-validation to evaluate the prediction performance. The Cross Entropy loss function is used to measure model performance in the expertise training stage. Adam optimizer is adopted to optimize all of the parameters in the model with a learning rate of 0.001. The batch size is setting to 32. The training epoch for each expertise model is 1500 at most. The drug and protein embedding size d_M, d_T is fixed to 128. The initialized atom feature vectors are described with DGL-LifeSci [10] package with the embedding size $f_M = 74$. The embedding size f_T of the initialized protein feature vectors is setting to 1200. The number of GCN, CNN, MLP layers L_M, L_T, L are all fixed to 3. The reward and penalty score β_R, β_P are both setting to 1.

For a fair comparison, the implementation of these OvO methods (SVM/GCN-based OvO) uses the same dive-and-conquer strategy as ours. In particular, GCN-based OvO shares the same network architecture as our method, except that the output of each sub-model does not include class \mathcal{N}_\otimes .

B.6 Experiment Compute Resources

All experiments are conducted by PyTorch on a single NVIDIA A6000 Tensor Core GPU (48GB) and Intel(R) Xeon CPU with 24 cores and 500G memory. The whole training time for all 28 sub-tasks of GtoPdb-MoA dataset is about 8 hours, and the inference time for test set is about 2 minutes.

B.7 Metric Details

This task involves a long-tailed multi-classification problem, where the ratio between the most frequent (head) class and the least frequent (tail) class is 132:1 (Figure 3). In such highly imbalanced scenarios, it is crucial to use evaluation metrics that provide a holistic view of model performance rather than favoring dominant classes. Given the total number of classes N , the accuracy and F1 score are explained in detail, highlighting why the F1 score is more appropriate for long-tailed classification tasks.

Accuracy. Accuracy is one of the most common metrics for classification problems and is defined as the ratio of correctly classified instances to the total number of instances.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (TP_n + TN_n)}{\sum_{n=1}^N (TP_n + TN_n + FP_n + FN_n)}.$$

Here, TP (True Positives) and TN (True Negatives) are the correctly classified positive and negative samples for class n , respectively, while FP (False Positives) and FN (False Negatives) are the misclassified instances for class n . Although accuracy is straightforward, it suffers in imbalanced datasets. In long-tailed distributions, accuracy is dominated by the head classes because the model tends to classify most instances as the majority class, thus overestimating performance while ignoring the minority classes.

F1 score. The F1 score [18] is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, effectively balancing these two metrics. In multi-class settings, precision and recall are calculated for each class, and the corresponding F1 score is then obtained. Finally, the F1 scores for all classes are averaged, which can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Precision}_n &= \frac{TP_n}{TP_n + FP_n}, & \text{Recall}_n &= \frac{TP_n}{TP_n + FN_n}, \\ \text{F1 score}_n &= 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision}_n \times \text{Recall}_n}{\text{Precision}_n + \text{Recall}_n}, \\ \text{F1 score} &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \text{F1 score}_n. \end{aligned}$$

The F1 score ranges from 0 to 1, where a higher value indicates a better balance between precision and recall. Unlike accuracy, the F1 score is less sensitive to class imbalance, making it particularly suitable for long-tailed tasks, as it ensures both head and tail classes contribute to the final evaluation.

Importance of F1 score in Long-Tailed Tasks. In long-tailed distributions, head classes often dominate accuracy due to their large sample size. However, for real-world problems like DTMoA prediction, correct predictions for tail classes are often more valuable. The F1 score provides a more nuanced view by equally weighing the importance of each class through the balance of precision and recall. This makes the F1 score the most critical metric in evaluating model performance under imbalanced conditions.

C Detail of Discussion

Detailed discussion about the proposed method is provided as follows. First, an additional discussion on specific experimental results is presented, focusing on the method’s superiority and applicability. Then, the motivation behind TED-DTMoA is introduced from a life sciences perspective, which arises from the synergistic relationship between the advancements in neuroscience and artificial intelligence.

Next, the advantage of promoting collaborative drug discovery is discussed in detail. In addition, the common solution for precious DTI methods is presented as a supplement of the main paper. Finally, the limitations of this study are thoroughly analyzed, and potential directions for future research are extensively discussed.

C.1 Additional Experimental Discussion

Solution for performance bottleneck. Figure 4b shows the performance relationship between each expertise model and overall prediction, demonstrating that the prediction performance of the overall multi-classification task depends on how well each expertise model handles its assigned task. In other words, the performance of TED-DTMoA is limited to the expertise models. Therefore, the leading solution for the performance bottleneck is to optimize the expertise models. Optimizing the performance of machine learning tasks can start with model architecture, hyper-parameter tuning, pretraining parameter initiation, and other settings. For the graph domain, the model selection set is GNN architecture and its variants [22]. In the future, the model architecture more suitable for the task can be completed automatically through strategies such as grid search [9] in machine learning. Similarly, the hyper-parameter of models can also be fine-tuned with the same strategy.

Potential application to other domains. Figure 4c shows the generalization of TED-DTMoA on a similar long-tailed DTMoA task, demonstrating that applying the proposed strategy to multi-classification or multi-label problems of other domains [7, 12, 19] is a potential and general solution to alleviate the existing long-tailed problems [5]. Specifically, each expertise model only needs to select two classes or labels and identify their similarities and differences. Then the prediction results of all expertise models are summarized to output the final prediction result. In the design process of the expertise models, no matter which field the input data comes from (audio, image, text, molecule SMILES, or others), it can be solved by using a simple backbone of the specific field. For example, ResNet architecture [3] can be considered as the expertise model to solve the classification sub-task between the cat and dog in the image field. Similarly, we can use Transformer architecture [20] as the encoder in the text field. Undoubtedly, more complex encoder architectures can also be used, depending on the user. Therefore, the proposed strategy can be easily applied to similar problems in different fields.

C.2 Neuroscience-inspired Motivation

The idea of tri-comparison expertise decision strategy originates from the evolution of human olfactory system. Over millions of years, the human olfactory system has gradually evolved to have the ability to perceive and distinguish various smells. Specifically, each olfactory receptor in the olfactory epithelium can recognize specific chemical structural features in odor molecules, that is, an odor molecule is decomposed into different chemical structural features and binds to specific receptors respectively, and then multiple electrical signals produced by the olfactory sensory neurons are transmitted to the high-level cognitive area for centralized decision-making and finally produce a judgment on the smell [13]. As the number and diversity of olfactory receptor genes gradually increase during the evolution of human body [15], the cognition of chemical structural characteristics of odor molecules is more accurate, and ultimately a more complex olfactory experience is formed. Therefore, the key to the essential function and evolvability of the olfactory system lies in the “function divide-central decision” olfactory receptor codes for odors.

Motivated by the perception process of human olfactory system, we try to mimic the “function divide-central decision” olfactory receptor codes for odors. Specifically, we disassemble the original complex multi-classification task into simple sub-tasks and assign the tasks to different expertise models, and then the class knowledge obtained by each model are ensembled together to make a comprehensive prediction for the original task. In order to comprehensively guide the own sub-task, the discrimination between the assigned task and all other tasks need to be determined, ensuring that the specific expertise can effectively achieve the assigned objective. This “function divide-central decision” mechanism not only achieves knowledge integration for multiple classes but also reduces the complexity of model learning and mitigates the effect caused by few samples.

C.3 Promotion for Collaborative Drug Discovery

The available volume of training data in drug discovery mainly determines the quality of intelligent models [17]. Consequently, the industry is making the first steps towards federated machine learning approaches that leverage more data than a single partner (e.g., a pharmaceutical company) [2].

The proposed tri-comparison expertise decision strategy can apply the mode of federated learning, which can effectively protect the security of data and models. On the one hand, each expertise model is only stored in the local terminal of each partner. The central processor only collects the prediction results of the expertise models for sub-tasks, and there is no exchange of specific information such as model parameters and gradients in this process; on the other hand, each expertise model only needs a moderate amount of labeled data from two different classes or labels during training, and there is no need for interaction of training data between expertise models. Even if the attackers get access to the interface of the central processor, they cannot obtain any specific information about data and models. Consequently, the strategy can effectively enhance the security of the DTMoA application systems and protect sensitive information.

C.4 Common Solution for Previous DTI Methods

In general, the common solution of previous DTI methods to address the DTI prediction problem is to adopt two encoders to translate the chemical information of drugs and proteins into feature representation and then output the interaction type with a decoder network after processing the combined feature.

In this process, the main difference is the encoder architecture for processing drug and target information. The biochemical structure of drugs can be represented by 1D SMILES [21] and 2D molecule graphs. Therefore, various 1D fingerprint generators and 2D encoder architectures are used to extract the feature information of drugs, such as Morgan fingerprint [14], Deep Neural Network [11], Graph Neural Network [22] or Transformer [20]. Meanwhile, since targets are usually represented by 1D protein sequences (too few data with 3D structures), it is generally encoded by architectures such as 1D Conventional Neural Network [6] or Transformer.

C.5 Limitation and Future Work

The divide-and-conquer strategy requires decomposing the original task into sub-tasks. As the number of classes N increases, the number of expertise models that need to be trained grows exponentially, potentially leading to a critical resource overload. Furthermore, even

though complex tasks are broken down into relatively simpler sub-tasks, issues such as class imbalance during the training process of the expertise models can still arise. These challenges may create performance bottlenecks, ultimately hindering further optimization of overall performance.

Future work will optimize TED-DTMoA with efficient learning algorithms to reduce resource use and enable dynamic selection of expertise models in constrained environments. We will investigate data augmentation techniques to address data imbalance and ensure balanced performance across classes. Finally, we will explore applications in other domains to better serve real-world scenarios, demonstrating the broader impact and versatility of our approach.

References

- [1] T. U. Consortium. UniProt: the Universal Protein Knowledgebase in 2023. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 51(D1):D523–D531, 11 2022. ISSN 0305-1048.
- [2] T. Hanser. Federated learning for molecular discovery. *Current Opinion in Structural Biology*, 79:102545, 2023. ISSN 0959-440X.
- [3] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 770–778, 2016.
- [4] K. Huang, T. Fu, L. M. Glass, M. Zitnik, C. Xiao, and J. Sun. DeepPurpose: a deep learning library for drug–target interaction prediction. *Bioinformatics*, 36(22-23):5545–5547, 12 2020. ISSN 1367-4803.
- [5] B. Kang, Y. Li, S. Xie, Z. Yuan, and J. Feng. Exploring balanced feature spaces for representation learning. In *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2020.
- [6] S. Kiranyaz, O. Avci, O. Abdeljaber, T. Ince, M. Gabbouj, and D. J. Inman. 1d convolutional neural networks and applications: A survey. *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 151:107398, 2021. ISSN 0888-3270.
- [7] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, and G. E. Hinton. Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 25, 2012.
- [8] G. Landrum. Rdkit: Open-source cheminformatics software. 2016. URL <https://www.rdkit.org>.
- [9] S. M. LaValle, M. S. Branicky, and S. R. Lindemann. On the relationship between classical grid search and probabilistic roadmaps. *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, 23(7-8):673–692, 2004.
- [10] M. Li, J. Zhou, J. Hu, W. Fan, Y. Zhang, Y. Gu, and G. Karypis. Dgl-lifesci: An open-source toolkit for deep learning on graphs in life science. *ACS Omega*, 6:27233–27238, 2021.
- [11] W. Liu, Z. Wang, X. Liu, N. Zeng, Y. Liu, and F. E. Alsaadi. A survey of deep neural network architectures and their applications. *Neurocomputing*, 234:11–26, 2017.
- [12] J. Long, E. Shelhamer, and T. Darrell. Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 3431–3440, 2015.
- [13] B. Malnic, J. Hirono, T. Sato, and L. B. Buck. Combinatorial receptor codes for odors. *Cell*, 96(5):713–723, 1999.
- [14] H. L. Morgan. The generation of a unique machine description for chemical structures—a technique developed at chemical abstracts service. *Journal of chemical documentation*, 5(2):107–113, 1965.
- [15] Y. Niimura and M. Nei. Evolution of olfactory receptor genes in the human genome. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 100(21):12235–12240, 2003.
- [16] Q. Pei, L. Wu, K. Gao, X. Liang, Y. Fang, J. Zhu, S. Xie, T. Qin, and R. Yan. BioT5+: Towards generalized biological understanding with IUPAC integration and multi-task tuning. In L.-W. Ku, A. Martins, and V. Srikumar, editors, *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2024*, pages 1216–1240, Bangkok, Thailand, Aug. 2024. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [17] B. Pejo, M. Remeli, A. Arany, M. Galtier, and G. Acs. Collaborative drug discovery: Inference-level data protection perspective. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.06506*, 2022.
- [18] M. Sokolova and G. Lapalme. A systematic analysis of performance measures for classification tasks. *Information processing & management*, 45(4):427–437, 2009.
- [19] C. Szegedy, A. Toshev, and D. Erhan. Deep neural networks for object detection. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 26, 2013.

- [20] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin. Attention is all you need. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 30, 2017.
- [21] D. Weininger. Smiles, a chemical language and information system. 1. introduction to methodology and encoding rules. *Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences*, 28(1):31–36, 1988.
- [22] Z. Wu, S. Pan, F. Chen, G. Long, C. Zhang, and S. Y. Philip. A comprehensive survey on graph neural networks. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*, 32(1):4–24, 2020.